

LiftWEC

DEVELOPMENT OF A NEW CLASS OF WAVE ENERGY CONVERTER
BASED ON HYDRODYNAMIC LIFT FORCES

Deliverable D9.2

Scoping report of the Environmental Impact Assessment

Deliverable Lead	WavEC Offshore Renewables
Delivery Date	30 th June 2021
Dissemination Level	Public
Status	Final
Version	1.0

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 851885. This output reflects the views only of the author(s), and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Document Information

Project Acronym	LiftWEC
Project Title	Development of a new class of wave energy converter based on hydrodynamic lift forces
Grant Agreement Number	851885
Work Package	WP09
Related Task(s)	T9.3
Deliverable Number	D9.2
Deliverable Name	Scoping report of the Environmental Impact Assessment
Due Date	31 st May 2021
Date Delivered	1 st July 2021
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Document Number	LW-D09-02

Version Control

Revision	Date	Description	Prepared By	Checked By
0.1	18/03/2021	Internal working draft	PAV, MA	MF, PLK
0.2	19/05/2021	Internal working draft	PAV, MA	MF, PLK
0.3	25/06/2021	Internal working draft	PAV, MF, PLK	BF, PLK
1.0	01/07/2021	Final report	PAV, BF	MF

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

LiftWEC is a collaborative research project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 851885. The LiftWEC project aims at identifying promising configurations of a Wave Energy Converter operating through the use of one or more rotating hydrofoils that generate lift as the primary interaction with the incident waves.

Under the project *Work Package 9 (WP9) – Environmental Impact Assessment*, four Tasks will be carried out to ensure the LiftWEC device development is made under the most suitable environmentally friendly criteria from an early design phase. The first WP9 Task (Task 9.1) resulted in a report (Deliverable 9.1¹) which identified the potential technology stressors from the LiftWEC installation and its effects on environmental and socioeconomic receptors.

The present document is developed under WP9 Task 9.3 and constitutes the second report of WP9: *Deliverable 9.2 – Scoping report of the Environmental Impact Assessment*. This report builds on D9.1 and further specifies the characteristics of the LiftWEC resulting in a preliminary Scoping report for the project Environmental Impact Assessment.

While a full EIA Scoping report cannot be developed at this stage of the LiftWEC device development, this document intends to include as much of the information required as possible and, when information is not fully available, indicative information will be presented based on experience in the sector and consultation within the consortium.

This report is divided into the following main Sections:

- Section 1: Introduction to the EIA Scoping
- Section 2: Description of the LiftWEC project
- Section 3: Baseline information for the foreseen installation site
- Section 4: Analysis of potential impacts and their mitigation
- Section 5: Monitoring of potential negative impacts
- Section 6: Concluding remarks

¹ <https://liftwec.com/d9-1-identification-of-potential-technology-stressors-environmental-receptors>

LIST OF ACRONYMS

AAM	Active Acoustic Monitoring
ADCP	Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler
AM	Adaptive Management
BD	Birds Directive
CTD	Conductivity, Temperature and Depth
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EMF	Electromagnetic Fields
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EU	European Union
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GIS	Geographic Information System
HD	Habitats Directive
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
LCOE	Levelized Cost Of Energy
MRE	Marine Renewable Energy
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
MBES	Multibeam Echo Sounders
OE	Ocean Energy
O&M	Operations & Maintenance
PAM	Active Acoustic Monitoring
ROV(s)	Remotely Operated Vehicle(s)
SAC(s)	Special Areas of Conservation (SACs)
SCI(s)	Sites of Community Importance
SONAR	Sound Navigation and Ranging
SPA(s)	Special Protection Areas
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WEC(s)	Wave Energy Converter(s)
WFD	Water Framework Directive

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 EIA FIRST STAGES

In the European Union, Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) must abide to the EIA Directive (Directive 2011/92/EU as amended by 2014/52/EU²) which identifies the projects³ subject to mandatory EIA (defined in Annex I of the Directive), and those for which EIA can be requested at the discretion of the Member States (defined in Annex II of the Directive). Marine Renewable Energy (MRE) projects are considered within Annex II of the EIA Directive, under the category “Energy industry: a) Industrial installations for the production of electricity (...)”

Although there is a significant variation in EIA procedures which is related with legal, policy and institutional frameworks in different countries, the EIA process can be summarized into seven main steps/phases (Figure 1.1):

Stepwise approach

1. Screening
2. Scoping
3. Baseline characterisation
4. Impact analysis
5. Mitigation measures
6. Public involvement
7. Monitoring

Figure 1.1: Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) process flow chart (adapted from: UNEP, 2002).

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32014L0052>

³ The EIA Directive Article 1(2) defines “Project” as “the execution of construction works or of other installations or schemes, other interventions in the natural surroundings and landscape including those involving the extraction of mineral resources”.

As the current report pertains to the Scoping report of the LiftWEC project, in the following subsections the EIA Scoping phase and its preceding Screening phase are briefly described (for descriptions of other EIA phases the reader is referred to Deliverable 9.1).

1.1.1 EIA Screening

The EIA Directive defines a common Screening approach to be adopted by Member States. Nonetheless, it is important that developers refer to Member State legislation to assess which requirements must be met.

During the Screening phase, the national authorities determine whether or not an EIA is needed, considering several criteria related to the project's characteristics (e.g., cumulation with other projects, use of natural resources, risks to the environment and to human health), its location (e.g., environmental sensitivity of the area, existing historical/cultural/archaeological features), and the type and characteristics of potential impacts (e.g., nature, magnitude, probability, reversibility of the impacts).

The Competent Authority decides about whether EIA is required. At the end of this stage, a Screening Decision must be issued and made public. If an EIA is required, the second step will be the Scoping.

1.1.2 EIA Scoping

The Scoping phase is an important step of the EIA as it provides the foundations for an effective and efficient EIA process. It provides an opportunity for both Developers and the Competent Authority to determine those key environmental impacts and issues of concern that are likely to be of the utmost importance to the Project proposal's decision-making and eliminates those that are less of a concern.

The Scoping aims, for example, to:

- Inform the public.
- Identify stakeholders.
- Evaluate concerns to identify significant issues.
- Organize and prioritise issues (for decision-making).
- Define the reasonable and practical alternatives for the project.
- Identify key environmental issues and significant impacts to be addressed.
- Define the temporal and spatial boundaries for the EIA.
- Set requirements for the collection of baseline information.

The EIA Directive allows the Developer to request a Scoping Opinion from the Competent Authority. While it is not mandatory for the Developer to request the Scoping Opinion, it is strongly encouraged as it may bring several benefits, for example:

- Allows focusing time and money resources on the important issues for decision-making and ensuring that resources are not spent on unnecessary assessments.
- Stimulates early consultation with the Competent Authority, environmental authorities, local and regional authorities, and the public.
- Helps to identify preliminary alternatives to the proposed Project as well as mitigation measures that should be considered by the Developer.

Although it may not be required by the Competent Authority, the Scoping Opinion can be mandatory in Member States that have set provisions in national legislation requiring it.

An important step of the Scoping is Consultation with environmental authorities and local and regional authorities. Consultations during Scoping will help to ensure that all of the impacts, issues, concerns, alternatives, and mitigation measures, which interested parties believe should be considered in the EIA, have been addressed. In the scope of the LiftWEC project, a Consultation exercise is being carried out under Task 9.2 and will result in the report *Deliverable 9.3 – Scoping report of the social acceptance of the final LiftWEC technology*.

1.2 LINKS TO OTHER EU LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORKS

1.2.1 Habitats Directive and Birds Directive

The EU Habitats Directive (HD; Directive 92/43/EEC⁴) and the EU Birds Directive (BD; Directive 79/409/EEC as amended by Directive 2009/147/EC⁵) form the cornerstone of Europe's nature conservation policy, establishing the EU Natura 2000 ecological network of protected areas aiming to “ensure the long-term survival of Europe's most valuable and threatened species and habitats”.

Member States choose sites according to precise, scientific criteria, but the selection procedure varies depending on which of the two Directives warrants the creation of a particular site. Under the HD Article 3 and Article 4, Member States designate Special Areas of Conservation (SACs) and Sites of Community Importance (SCIs) to ensure the favourable conservation status of each habitat type and species throughout their range in the EU. Under the BD Article 4, Member States define Special Protection Areas (SPAs) designated for a number of particularly threatened species and all migratory bird species.

Any Project likely to have a significant effect on a Natura 2000 site is subject to an Appropriate Assessment of the implications for the site in view of the site's conservation objectives (HD Article 6(3)⁶). The Appropriate Assessment decision is binding and determines whether a Project may proceed, subject to specific provisions set out in Article 6(4).

1.2.2 Water Framework Directive

The EU Water Framework Directive (WFD; Directive 2000/60/EC⁷) establishes a framework for the protection of inland surface waters, transitional waters, coastal waters, and groundwater.

Projects that may lead to failure of achieving “good status” of water bodies or lead to deterioration of quality elements need to be assessed. If possible, a more environmentally friendly alternative should be found. If no alternative can be found, then the Project will need to demonstrate that (i) all mitigation measures are taken to reduce the impact, and (ii) the reasons for deterioration are of

⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31992L0043>

⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32009L0147>

⁶ The Habitat Directive Article 6(3) states that “any plan or project not directly connected with or necessary to the management of the site but likely to have a significant effect thereon, either individually or in combination with other plans or projects, shall be subject to appropriate assessment of its implications for the site in view of the site's conservation objectives”.

⁷ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32000L0060>.

overriding public interest or that the Project's benefits otherwise outweigh failure to achieve the relevant environmental objectives (WFD Article 4(7)).

1.2.3 Marine Strategy Framework directive

The EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD; Directive 2008/56/EC⁸) establishes a framework to assess and implement "good environmental status" of marine waters. The MSFD takes an ecosystem and integrated approach whereby environmental protection and sustainable use go hand in hand to prevent depletion of natural resources upon which marine-related economic and social activities are based.

The "good environmental status" is assessed by considering 11 Descriptors, several of which (e.g., D1: Biodiversity, D4: Seafloor integrity) can be affected by MRE developments.

1.2.4 Waste Framework Directive

The Waste Framework Directive (Directive 2008/98/EC⁹) establishes a legal framework for the management and treatment of most waste types.

The Directive sets out a waste hierarchy that ranges from prevention to disposal. Waste management under the Directive must be implemented without endangering human health and without harming the environment (e.g., without risk to water, air, biodiversity, and without causing nuisance). It also sets out rules for extended producer responsibility, effectively adding to the burdens of manufacturers to manage products returned after use.

1.3 OTHER POLICY REQUIREMENTS

There are several consents and licences, both for offshore and onshore activities/uses, that will be required to implement the Project at a specific location. The requirements will depend on regional and national legal frameworks and will need to be determined in consultation with the relevant authorities.

2 LIFTWEC PROJECT OVERVIEW

2.1 THE PROPOSED DEVELOPMENT

LiftWEC is a Horizon 2020 Research Project focused on the development of a lift-based Wave Energy Converter (WEC) whose primary coupling with the waves is through hydrodynamic lift forces.

A small number of lift-based WECs have been proposed, generally being designed considering idealised wave conditions, where the ocean waves are assumed to be regular sinusoidal oscillations. The LiftWEC project will develop the concept of utilising wave-induced lift forces to extract energy in irregular ocean waves. The concept involves consideration of the irregularity of waves as a fundamental element of the design.

The objective of LiftWEC project is to determine the potential of this concept to produce renewable energy at a commercially competitive price whilst ensuring a minimal environmental/social impact.

⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32008L0056>.

⁹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02008L0098-20180705>.

This will be achieved by a combination of numerical/physical modelling and desk-based studies of the structural design, the operational & maintenance requirements, and the environmental/social impacts of the technology. The numerical/physical modelling will demonstrate the concept's performance, thereby taking the concept from Technology Readiness Level 1 (TRL 1) to TRL 4, whilst the desk-based studies will allow the socially-acceptable commercial potential to be determined.

2.2 THE DEVELOPER

The LiftWEC project is carried out by a consortium of 10 participants from 6 different European countries and is structured into 11 work-packages (WP) that define the major groups of activities to be carried out (Table 2.1). The participants are specialists and world-leading in the aspects for which they are responsible in the project.

Table 2.1: List of LiftWEC project Consortium participants.

Participant	Country	Responsibility
The Queen's University of Belfast	UK	Coordinator Leads WP1: Project management Leads WP2: Concept development and evaluation Leads WP10: Dissemination and exploitation Leads WP11: Ethics requirements
Technische Universitat Hamburg	Germany	Leads WP3: Numerical modelling
National University of Ireland Maynooth	Ireland	Leads WP5: Control strategy
Innosea	France	
Aalborg Universitet	Denmark	Leads WP8: Cost of energy
University College Cork	Ireland	Leads WP7: Operation and maintenance design
Ecole Centrale de Nantes	France	Leads WP4: Physical modelling
Julia Chozas Consulting	Denmark	
WavEC Offshore Renewables	Portugal	Leads WP9: Environmental impact assessment
University of Strathclyde	UK	Leads WP6: Structural design

2.3 THE TECHNOLOGY

At the end of the first LiftWEC project workshop (25-27 May 2020), 17 preliminary LiftWEC configurations¹⁰ were generated through discussions among researchers from each participant (project Milestone 1). Since then, several discussions and analyses have been and will be undertaken aiming at reducing the potential LiftWEC configurations to the minimum number and pushing to more specific prototypes (Milestone 2).

The technology presented in this report is expected to be representative of the LiftWEC device at the completion of the LiftWEC project (Dec 2022) based on current understanding as it exists today (June 2021). However, there is still a large amount of uncertainty relating to the influence of design decisions

¹⁰ Details in the LiftWEC project *Deliverable 2.3 – Review of Current Lift-Based WEC Concepts and Specification of Preliminary Configurations*, available at <https://liftwec.com/d2-3-review-of-current-lift-based-wec-concepts-and-specification-of-preliminary-configurations>.

on device viability from practically all perspectives (hydrodynamic, structural, environmental etc.) and as such, the details proposed are subject to change.

At present, WP2 has primarily considered the design of systems which are phase-locked relative to the incident water waves. The expected device characteristics for a phase-locked device of this type are presented in the following subsections.

2.3.1 Number of Hydrofoils

It is expected that LiftWEC most likely will have either 2 or 3 hydrofoils. If the control requirement for LiftWEC is able to maximise power capture, LiftWEC would have 2 hydrofoils. If it proves difficult to control LiftWEC in irregular seas, LiftWEC would probably have 3 hydrofoils. At present, having 2 hydrofoils is the aim.

2.3.2 Operational Radius

The operational radius of LiftWEC refers to the distance from the axis of rotation to the position of the hydrofoil. If it is assumed that LiftWEC will have 2 hydrofoils, LiftWEC is expected to require operational radii ranging from approximately 6-12 m to achieve maximum power capture across the range of seas of interest, i.e. maintaining performance in both small and large seas. LiftWEC may be designed such that the radius can be modified on a per sea-state basis. That is, the radius might be varied for each 0.5 m shift in significant wave height, or 1 second shift in period, so possibly every 10-30 minutes. Based on the 6-12 m operational radius and the variation in desirable radius with wave period, the maximum linear speed of the hydrofoil is expected to be between 6-12 m/s.

2.3.3 Width/Span

The width, or span, of LiftWEC refers to its dimension parallel to the incident wave crest. It is expected that the span of LiftWEC will range between approximately 18-60 m, and more likely between 18-30 m. The smaller LiftWEC is in this dimension, the lower the rated power of each individual device which will mean that there are more individual units to constitute a 100 MW wave farm.

2.3.4 Operational water depth

It is expected that the minimum water depth in which LiftWEC would be deployed is approximately 25 m. In truth, from a device design perspective, this depth might be slightly shallower than ideal. With LiftWEC ideal operational radius approaching 12 m for a 10 second, 4 m wave, it is possible that moving further offshore might be ideal due to the requirements for increased operational radii in larger seas. The current expectation is that deployment is made in water depths of 40-100 m, however this is very provisional.

2.3.5 Submergence

It would seem that LiftWEC should be located as close to the surface as possible without being so close as to ever pierce the free water surface. In fact, LiftWEC should probably stay at least a few metres away from the free surface to avoid loss of lift. At present, it would seem that if LiftWEC is to achieve operational radii of up to 6-12 m, an ideal submergence (to the axis of rotation) might be 9-15 m.

2.3.6 Device rating and number of devices

From the work developed so far, it is expected that LiftWEC will achieve Capture Width Ratios in the range of 0.5-0.8 in irregular seas. That means that the system can convert an average of approximately 50-80% of the available energy across its width into useful energy. The system will also dissipate some

of the incident wave energy through drag and viscous losses. It is possible that this value will increase, however, this is a conservative estimate.

If a Capture Width Ratio of 0.75 is assumed, and a moderate sea with an energy period of 10 seconds and a significant wave height of 3 m is considered, then the incident wave power per metre of wave crest is approximately 43 kW/m. This allows us to determine an approximate rating for the LiftWEC device. If it is assumed a device width of approximately 31 m, a device power train rating of approximately 1 MW ($0.75 \times 43 \times 31$) is required. In this case, there would be 100 devices in the 100 MW wave farm. Using the expected Capture Width Ratios above and the expected widths of devices, then each device is likely to be rated between 500 kW-2 MW. Thus, a farm consisting of 50–200 devices is expected.

2.3.7 Maritime area required

As mentioned in section 2.3.6, for a rated wave of 10 seconds, 3 m height, it was assumed approximately 75% of the energy would be captured. This means capturing 75% of 43 kW for every metre of LiftWEC deployed. Then, to capture 100 MW approximately 2,400 m of LiftWEC must be deployed aligned along the wave crest. From a power capture perspective, if this is composed of 50 devices each of 48 m length or 200 devices each of 12 m length is not relevant. However, if it is assumed that no more than 25 % of the wave energy is to be removed across the farm, then the devices should be spaced out across 3 times that length ($75 \% / 25 \% = 3$). Then, the entire farm would span approximately 7.5 km of wave crest. The width of this line would be minimal, possibly 100 m to include mooring lines, hence, the total area of sea occupied would be approximately 0.75 km².

2.3.8 Stability elements

There is likely to be between 1-4 anchors (and mooring lines where appropriate) per device, where in some cases the anchors may be shared by two devices. Thus, with 50–200 devices it means that there would be 50–800 anchors in the wave farm. It is likely that where more anchors are needed, the size of each anchor will be smaller.

At present, three main types of configurations can be described¹¹: 1) monopile supported, 2) V-frame supported, and 3) floating.

2.3.8.1 Monopile supported configuration

A LiftWEC configuration supported by a monopile is presented in Figure 2.1. The radius of the LiftWEC rotor is 3 m. The monopile has an outer diameter of 3 m and a height of 53 m (assuming a 50 m water depth). It is assumed that one third of the monopile (~17 m) is embedded in the soil, hence, ~36 m of monopile are positioned from the seabed to the water column. The rotor is supported by a bracket structure with bearings at each side. The central shaft is connected to bearings, which are inserted in the bracket structure. Lateral spokes support the hydrofoils. The central shaft is hollow with an outer diameter 1.2 m.

The computed volumes and masses of the substructures are shown in Table 2.2. The total mass of device (without monopile) is approximately 260 tonnes. The mass of the monopile is 734 tonnes.

¹¹ The information on the three main types of configurations was retrieved from LiftWEC project *Deliverable 6.2 – Transportation and Maintenance LiftWEC ULS Assessment*, available at <https://liftwec.com/d6-2-transportation-and-maintenance-liftwec-uls-assessment>.

Figure 2.1: Monopile supported configuration of LiftWEC.

Table 2.2: Volume, density, total mass, and percentage mass of substructures of the LiftWEC monopile supported configuration. The material selected is offshore structural steel.

Substructure	Quantity	Unit volume (m ³)	Density (kg/m ³)	Total Mass (tonnes)	Total mass (%)
Hydrofoils	2	9.0	7850	142	12.9
Rotor	1	15.1	7850	118	10.7
Spokes	4	0.1	7850	2	0.2
Support bracket	1	13.1	7850	103	9.4
Monopile	1	94.0	7850	734	66.8
Total	1	561.6	7850	1099	100.0

2.3.8.2 V-frame supported configuration

A LiftWEC configuration supported by a V-frame is presented in Figure 2.2. The V-frame structure can be retractable, similarly to the support structure of CycWEC (Siegel, 2019) or fixed and independently transported. The dimensions of the rotor are the same as those of the monopile case. The frame is built with solid bars with a diameter of 1 m.

The computed volumes and masses of the substructures are shown in Table 2.3. Like for the monopile supported configuration, the total mass of device (without V-frames) is approximately 260 tonnes. The mass of each V-frame is approximately 500 tonnes.

Figure 2.2: V-frame supported configuration of LiftWEC.

Table 2.3: Volume, density, total mass, and percentage mass of substructures of the LiftWEC V-frame supported configuration. The material selected is offshore structural steel.

Substructure	Quantity	Unit volume (m ³)	Density (kg/m ³)	Total Mass (tonnes)	Total mass (%)
Hydrofoils	2	9.0	7850	142	11.3
Rotor	1	15.1	7850	118	9.5
Spokes	4	0.1	7850	2	0.1
Frame	2	63.0	7850	986	79.0
Total	1	561.6	7850	1248	100.0

2.3.8.3 Floating configuration

A LiftWEC floating configuration is presented in Figure 2.3. The dimensions of the rotor are the same as the previous ones. The floater is constructed with 3 cylinders of an outer diameter of 3 m and a height of 5 m. The connecting rods of the floater have a 1 m diameter.

The computed volumes and masses of the substructures are shown in Table 2.4. Like for the two other configurations, the total mass of the device (without floater) is approximately 260 tonnes. The mass of the floater is estimated to be 276 tonnes.

Figure 2.3: Floating configuration of LiftWEC.

Table 2.4: Volume, density, total mass, and percentage mass of substructures of the LiftWEC floating configuration. The material selected is offshore structural steel.

Substructure	Quantity	Unit volume (m ³)	Density (kg/m ³)	Total Mass (tonnes)	Total mass (%)
Hydrofoils	2	9.0	7850	142	22.1
Rotor	1	15.1	7850	118	18.5
Spokes	4	0.1	7850	2	0.3
Support bracket	1	13.1	7850	103	16.1
Floater	1	35.2	7850	276	43.1
Total	1	561.6	7850	641	100.0

2.3.9 Area occupied in the water column

Considering the range of water depths of 25-100 m and operational radii of 6–12 m, then the occupation of the water column is likely to be 12-50 %, where the occupation will be in the bottom part of the water column for the monopile and V-frame configurations, or in the top part for the floating configuration. Although the monopile and V-Frame configurations may represent greater vertical occupation of the water column compared to the floating configuration, those two will be static structures that should allow marine animals and physical-chemical processes to occur naturally.

2.3.10 Materials

At present it is considered to be preferable for the hydrofoils to be formed from a composite material, although steel is also possible. The supporting structure will likely be of marine grade steel with concrete and grouting in the foundations.

2.3.11 Generator

It is likely that an electrical generator will be used, which may also include a gearbox. The gearbox may contain a lubricant, probably the same as would be used in a ship propeller and drive system.

2.4 MARINE OPERATIONS

Careful planning of marine operations is of utmost importance to reduce costs and make the technology attractive to private investors. The installation costs typically represent 20% of the project Levelized Cost Of Energy (LCOE) and Operations & Maintenance (O&M) activities represent 13.1-56.5% of the project LCOE (Poulsen et al., 2017). The Ocean energy (OE) sector usually follows O&M strategies developed for the offshore wind industry (Martin et al., 2016) which is at a much more advanced stage than the OE sector. Several standards have been developed by DNV GL, LOC and ISO which provide guidance for designing, planning, and executing marine operations in the MRE sector (Table 2.5)

Table 2.5: List of standards with guidance on designing, planning, and execution of marine operations (Fonseca, 2021a).

<u>Design and planning phase:</u>	<u>Execution phase:</u>	<u>Operation specifics:</u>
Numerical modelling of the assets dynamic responses to environmental conditions	Modelling operations, reducing operational limits based on forecast conditions	
- DNV OS H102	- DNV OS H101	- DNV OS H201 Load-out, mating
- DNV OS H206	- GL Noble Denton, General guidelines for MO	- DNV OS H205 part 2-5 Lifting operations
- DNV RP-C205	- LOC, Guidelines for MO	- DNV OS H206 Load-out, transport, installation of subsea objects
- DNV CN 30.5	- ISO 19901-6 Marine operations O&G	
- ISO 19901-1 environmental conditions	- ISO 29400 Ships & Marine Tech.	
- DNV RP-H103	Offshore wind energy-Port and MO	
	- NORSOK Marine Operations	

Marine operations in the MRE sector are distinguished into three main types of activities (Fonseca, 2021b):

i) Installation activities

- Foundation installation
- (Pre-lay) mooring installation
- Cable installation
- Collection point installation
- Device installation

ii) Maintenance activities

- Small repairs
- Visual inspections
- Subsea inspections (ROVs, divers)
- Large component replacements

iii) Decommissioning activities

- Device removal
- Collection point removal
- Moorings removal

- Decommissioning of foundations
- Cable removal

The next subsections describe what can be envisaged for the LiftWEC installation, maintenance, and decommissioning activities.

2.4.1 Installation methods

2.4.1.1 *Offshore components*

The LiftWEC installation will include the following offshore components:

- Device
- Foundation
- Moorings and anchors
- Subsea electrical infrastructure (hub) and subsea export cable
- Navigation markings

Different installation works are foreseen during two main stages: i) site preparation and surveys, and ii) construction.

i) Site preparation and surveys

This stage will comprise seabed surveys and any ground investigation work that is required (e.g., including archaeological surveys). This will be necessary to establish the physical characteristics of the seabed in the area of installation of the devices and cable routes. This is likely to include the removal of sediment and rock by grab sampling, diver surveys and/or rotary drilling. Where cables are likely to be installed in trenches or by directional drilling, the physical characteristics of substrates beneath the seabed will need to be investigated covering the cables route to the shore. This may involve rotary core drilling and/or boreholes.

ii) Construction

The assembly of devices can be done at port or on site, and the strategy should be based on balancing the trade-offs. For example, assembly at port allows for simpler, safer, and cheaper operations but the fully assembled components required greater storage space. On the other hand, assembly on site allows more components to be transported per trip, but operations are more dangerous and are more dependent on by sea state requirements.

Different methods can be used for the transportation of devices and components (Fonseca, 2021b), each with their own advantages and constraints, namely:

- On deck
 - Transported to site on deck of the main vessel
 - Component is transported to site on deck of the main vessel
 - Requires sufficient deck area and deck cargo capacity
 - As components get larger, vessels become more expensive
- Dry towing
 - Transported to site on deck of a non-propelled barge, which is towed to site by tow vessel(s)
 - Requires a towing vessel with sufficient pulling force (bollard pull) to tow the barge

- Tow may be carried out using multiple vessels for increased stability
- Wet towing
 - Placed in the water and towed to site)
 - At port, component is placed in the water and towed to site
 - Requires vessel(s) with sufficient bollard pull to tow the component
 - For increased stability and safety, multiple towing vessels may be used
 - Reduces requirements for heavy lifts on site
 - Components being wet-towed must be structurally designed for the purpose

During the construction stage, the first activity should be installing the export cable from shore out to the array installation site, as well as a hub on site connected to the export cable.

After, the foundations of LiftWEC devices should be installed in the offshore location, the methods for which will depend on the type of LiftWEC configuration – monopile supported, V-frame supported, or floating configuration:

- **Monopile configuration**

The monopile configuration will require a large vessel (heavy lift or jack up) as it will be at least 70 m (50 m water depth plus submerged depth). The monopile (and V-frame) will require some scour protection at the intersection between the seabed and the support structure. Scour is the erosion of sediment around a structure, which can lead to exposure of the support structure at the seabed, reducing the resistive loads and potentially leading to catastrophic failure. The solution typically involves depositing rocks in an armour layer at the base of the support structure.

- **V-frame configuration**

The V-frame foundation (being a relatively large structure) may require similar vessels for installation, comparable to a jacket type foundation for offshore wind. Connection and reconnection of a device to the V-frame foundation might be easier as it may be towed out and connected to the piles (in comparison to monopiles where the device would have to be lifted on/off).

Alternatively if the V-frame structure follows the installation strategy of the CYCWEC device (Siegel, 2019), then smaller towing vessels may be used for installation. This configuration uses extendable struts allowing the legs/struts to be compactly folded for towing during transportation to site, whereupon the legs are then extended using a jack up mechanism to pre-installed seabed moorings. The mooring points can be implemented using suction caissons, driven piles, drilled rock anchors or any other suitable technology depending on ocean floor bathymetry.

- **Floating configuration**

The floating configuration will require some seabed preparation work with the installation of drag anchors at the seabed. Depending on the required resistive forces, larger Ancho Handling Tug vessels may be required, which are the only vessels capable of generating the necessary bollard pull, to suitably install such fixings, as is the case for some floating wind configurations.

After the installation of foundations, inter-array cables (comprising cables between individual devices) should then be connected to the devices and to the hub. This will reduce the number of export cables to the shore. The cables may be positioned buried into the seabed or laid on it and covered by an

armouring or mattress protection (e.g., rock armouring or concrete mattresses) to protect and stabilise the cables on the seabed. The landfall location of the export cable will need to be defined, but the cable should be buried so it remains invisible to beach users.

Finally, the devices should be wet towed¹² (in case the assembly is at port) from the nearest suitable port (which in the current scenario is in Brest) to the installation site, where it is deployed, moored, and connected to the hub.

Considering the 110 km distance between the Brest port and the installation site, and a towing velocity of 3 kn (5.56 km/h), this means 20 h will be needed to tow a device. Each foundation should take up to five days to be installed. Spreading the moorings should take two days and connecting the cables to the foundation and to the hub should take one more day. Table 2.6 provides details to the time needed for transportation and installation activities.

Table 2.6: Time expended in transportation and installation activities.

	Monopile supported / V-frame supported	Floating
Transportation (110 km)		
Electrical cables	3h port work + 20h towing to site + 5h vessel back to port	
Anchors + moorings	8h port work per mooring line + 20h towing to site + 5h vessel back to port	
Foundation	3h port work + 20h towing to site + 5h vessel back to port	-
Device	3h port work + 20h towing to site + 5h vessel back to port	
Installation		
Anchoring + moorings pre-laying	5h per mooring line	
Cable laying (ploughing, medium dense sand; 10 km export cable)	61h	
Foundation	24-48 h	-
Device	9h	
Bad weather contingencies	+ 30% time	

Navigational marker buoys need to be installed to identify the position of the Project during operation (minimum four buoys defining North, South, East, and West boundaries). The buoys must be appropriately anchored and inspected frequently. This will minimize the potential for damage of the anchors and potential drifting of the buoys which can pose navigational hazards.

The marine operations should take place preferably during the months when weather conditions are more favourable (i.e., in spring, summer, or autumn), also avoiding the busiest tourist periods.

The number and types of vessels involved in the installation process will be determined following a review of similar installation activities for other WE installations, as well as discussion with marine contractors and the detailed design of array components. Vessels considered likely to be involved in

¹² According to the LiftWEC project Deliverable 6.2, wet towing should be adequate for the transportation of the LiftWEC device.

installation method include Dynamic Positioning vessels, Jack-up barges, tugs, dive boats, and workboats.

2.4.1.2 Onshore components

The onshore components will consist of:

- Substation compound
- Connection to the grid
- Access road

The onshore works will involve a cable landfall through the intertidal zone, junction box to connect the marine cables to terrestrial, a substation compound and grid connection works to the existing electricity distribution network.

Similarly to the export cable, the onshore cable should be buried. The junction box may be either an underground chamber or above ground infrastructure close to the shore.

The substation compound will house the substation, transformers, and any other electronics required. The substation will be connected to the local electricity distribution network, which likely will involve a single underground cable connection. The existing network should remain in place and not be affected by the development.

The exact location of onshore works and the area required for components should be determined in the ES. The works carried out onshore (e.g., construction of the substation, grid connection and any associated grid reinforcement works, construction of access roads) are subject to separate consents and approvals.

2.4.2 Operations and maintenance activities

The LiftWEC Consortium has worked, and will continue working, towards achieving a device concept and design that allow maximum ease of operations and maintenance (O&M).

Maintenance operations may involve the use of divers or Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVs) for minor external activities or the recovery of individual components. Depending on the works and sea state, the works may be carried out on site. For maintenance of a LiftWEC device, it will be disconnected from the inter-array cabling, foundation, and moorings (which will be left on the seabed) and, depending on the maintenance needs, lifted onto the maintenance barge or vessel, and wet towed or carried on deck to the port where it will be subjected to maintenance works.

Automated failsafe procedures should be provided to ensure that during a situation where power or communications from the shore is lost, a device shuts down immediately to a safe state.

Preventive and corrective maintenance activities are foreseen. Preventive maintenance will be undertaken according to scheduled services whereas corrective maintenance would be needed for example to cover unexpected repairs or component replacements.

2.5 DECOMMISSIONING

At the end of its operational life (25 years or more) the Project will be decommissioned, and the seabed and onshore facets returned to their original condition. The operations should be relatively straightforward, following the same relative sequence used in installation, but in reverse.

The possibility of partial removal instead of full removal of MRE structures/equipment upon decommissioning has been debated recently. Although the OSPAR Decision on the Disposal of Disused Offshore Installations (OSPAR Commission, 1998) requires that artificial structures be fully removed from the maritime space (with some exceptions), the removal of artificial structures (e.g., cables, scour protection rocks) is considered not only to cause substantial damage and disruption to the seabed but also potential loss of the biodiversity created by the artificial reef effect during the operational phase (e.g., Topham and McMillan, 2017; Coolen et al., 2020).

The LiftWEC devices would have material components similar to that of a wind turbine (e.g., steel, composites, copper, electrical equipment). Therefore, some indication of the reuse, recycle and disposal of materials can be gained from observation of the offshore wind industry (McAuliffe et al., 2019). The hydrofoil blades are likely to be a composite material with some fibreglass make up. This material is not suitable for recycling and will therefore have to be disposed of at the end of the devices lifetime. The transformer and power convertors may be suitable for resale, depending on their condition. Copper and steel components of the generator may be recycled as can any steel from the support structure or main device hub.

A more detailed decommissioning plan and programme should be developed and be updated during the project's lifespan to take account of changing legal requirements, best-practice procedures, and new technologies at the time to minimise the environmental impact.

2.6 PROJECT TIMESCALE

During Year 0 and part of Year 1, detailed geotechnical surveys of the site must be undertaken to determine the precise locations of the LiftWEC devices and establish the most appropriate foundation option(s). During this period, baseline surveys (e.g., to characterize the marine habitats and organisms in the area) should also be conducted.

At the start of Year 1, the installation of the foundation can be prepared and carried out.

This will be followed by the installation of the LiftWEC device, which should be deployed for up to five years, during which it should be tested, calibrated, and optimized.

At the end of this period, the single device will either be decommissioned or incorporated into the larger array, subject to the relevant permissions.

It should be highlighted that to achieve the installation of a full array of devices, different project applications are required for the different stages of the project, including the installation and testing of a single demonstration-device (or a low number of devices), full scale device(s) and an array of commercial-scale devices. Each stage will be subject to individual consenting and permitting whose approval will depend on the country where it is issued and the project characteristics, among others. In France, for example, consenting and permitting application for each phase may take up to 4 years (ETIP Ocean, 2020¹³).

Table 2.7 provides a summarized timescale for a single LiftWEC device installation.

¹³ Available at <https://www.etipocean.eu/assets/Uploads/ETIP-Ocean-Ocean-energy-and-the-environment.pdf>

Table 2.7: Timescale for the installation, operation and decommissioning of a LiftWEC single device.

Task	Year						
	0		1		7		
	Q1-4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1-2	Q3-4
Detailed site surveys							
Installation of foundation							
Transport and installation of subsystems (e.g., moorings, electrical cabling)							
Installation of LiftWEC device							
Operation of LiftWEC single device							
Decommissioning of LiftWEC single device							

2.7 POTENTIAL SITE LOCATION

EIA Regulations require Applicants to outline how chosen options have been selected and the reasonable alternatives considered by the Applicant. At present, the final site location for the LiftWEC installation is yet to be determined, which makes difficult to indicate alternative options. Therefore, these will not be included in this report.

The project location selected will need to consider several criteria, such as wave resource, seabed conditions, human activity and use of maritime space (e.g., fisheries, tourism), required infrastructure, port facilities, and environmental constraints (e.g., presence of marine protected sites or habitats in the area), among others. It should, for example:

- Be exposed to the predominant wave direction to maximize power generation
- Be relatively close to land, close to a major port, and close to potential grid connection, for economic and operational purposes
- Avoid protected or sensitive areas of Conservation
- Avoid areas where endangered/threatened species are present
- Avoid critical wildlife migration routes
- Avoid important areas of local income (e.g., fishing, boating)

It is assumed that the LiftWEC farm will be located in the North East Atlantic waters. It is foreseen that the array of devices is installed offshore the Audierne Bay (France) in a bathymetry of 50 m, hence, between the coordinates 47.84° N, 4.43° W (<https://maps.ngdc.noaa.gov/viewers/bathymetry>) at about 6 km from shore (Figure 2.4). To achieve the 100 MW goal, the array may occupy an extent of 0.75 km² (see details in 2.3.7), the length and width of which will depend on the arrangement of devices (e.g., straight line vs. mosaic of devices) (Figure 2.4).

The nearest port suitable for service vessels and for installation vessels is in Brest, at about 110 km of the foreseen installation site.

Confirmation of the exact location of the devices, subsystems (e.g., moorings) and electrical cabling routes should be identified once further site surveys have been undertaken and presented in the Environmental Statement.

Figure 2.4: Location foreseen for LiftWEC deployment. Different sections of maritime space will be used according to the devices arrangement, for example a straight line of devices (yellow symbols) vs. a mosaic of devices (orange symbols).

3 BASELINE INFORMATION

This section includes baseline information resultant from a preliminary desk-based work for the area of Audierne Bay. At the time of the EIA report, more specific and detailed baseline information of the final installation site will need to be presented (e.g., collected from monitoring surveys of the area, development plans, databases, and scientific reports and published papers).

3.1 PHYSICAL ENVIRONMENT

3.1.1 Wave resource characterisation

The reference wave regime is taken from the North Atlantic coast of France close to Quimper at 47.84° N, 4.83° W. A scatter table detailing the percentage occurrence of given sea states is presented in Figure 3.1. From consideration of the scatter table, it is evident that the vast majority of incident seas ($> 88\%$) have a significant wave height of less than 4 m, however extreme seas with significant wave heights $> 8\text{m}$ are recorded on at least an annual basis. Incident sea states with less than 2m significant wave height account for approximately 34 % of all seas.

Total	0.00	0.02	1.23	7.12	16.12	20.17	18.91	14.60	10.58	6.30	2.98	1.32	0.49	0.11	0.05	100.00
8.00								0.00	0.01	0.11	0.11	0.08	0.05	0.01		0.37
7.50								0.00	0.04	0.09	0.09	0.03	0.03	0.00		0.30
7.00								0.04	0.10	0.13	0.07	0.05	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.43
6.50								0.00	0.08	0.18	0.21	0.11	0.05	0.02	0.00	0.66
6.00								0.03	0.27	0.40	0.34	0.16	0.08	0.02	0.00	1.31
5.50								0.14	0.49	0.48	0.38	0.12	0.07	0.02	0.01	1.72
5.00						0.02	0.46	0.75	0.69	0.55	0.19	0.08	0.06	0.01		2.80
4.50						0.15	0.85	0.97	0.87	0.39	0.24	0.10	0.02	0.01	0.01	3.61
4.00				0.03	0.53	1.16	1.16	1.14	0.94	0.58	0.33	0.11	0.03	0.01	0.00	4.86
3.50				0.26	1.07	1.44	1.44	1.19	1.01	0.58	0.27	0.14	0.05	0.00	0.00	6.02
3.00			0.04	0.94	2.07	1.81	1.75	1.29	0.77	0.36	0.14	0.04	0.01	0.00		9.22
2.50			0.00	0.37	2.61	3.27	2.90	2.18	1.52	0.84	0.47	0.18	0.08	0.01	0.00	14.42
2.00			0.06	1.36	3.90	4.28	4.39	2.92	1.85	0.93	0.33	0.14	0.03	0.01		20.19
1.50			0.56	3.22	4.93	5.87	4.30	2.28	0.95	0.30	0.11	0.07	0.01	0.01	0.02	22.63
1.00	0.02	0.60	2.08	3.38	2.85	1.39	0.53	0.23	0.08	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00		11.19
0.50		0.00	0.06	0.08	0.07	0.04	0.01									0.26
	3.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	7.0	8.0	9.0	10.0	11.0	12.0	13.0	14.0	15.0	16.0	17.0	Total

Figure 3.1: Percentage occurrence of given sea states.

3.1.2 Geology and submerged landscapes

According to the EMODnet Geology portal (<https://www.emodnet-geology.eu>), in the Audierne Bay the seabed substrate is mainly sandy in the lower section and rocky in the upper section (Figure 3.2). The Bay also includes sections of mud, muddy sand, and coarse substrate. The lower section of the Bay may be subject to coastal erosion (Figure 3.2).

No submerged landscapes in the Audierne Bay are identified by the EMODnet Geology portal.

Figure 3.2: Seabed substrate (left) and coastal migration (right) in the Audierne Bay.

3.2 BIOLOGICAL ENVIRONMENT

3.2.1 Protected areas

According to EMODnet Human Activities portal (<https://emodnet.eu/en/human-activities>), the coastal area close to the LiftWEC implementation site include sections of National Designated Areas regarded in the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Category IV: Habitat/Species Management Area. The area includes sections of Natura 2000, with SPAs (1709 ha) encompassed in the BD and SCIs (2455.75 ha) encompassed in the HD (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3: National Designated Areas (A.) and Natura 2000 areas (B.) close to the LiftWEC implementation area.

3.2.2 Seabed habitats

The EUNS habitat mapping was retrieved from the EMODnet Seabed Habitats portal (<https://www.emodnet-seabedhabitats.eu>) for the area encompassing the maritime to onshore area. It was used the *Broad-scale EUNIS habitat maps - full detail* system.

Several habitats were identified in the area (Figure 3.4), namely:

- A1 – Littoral rock and other hard substrata
- A2 – Litoral sediment
- A3 – Infralittoral rock and other hard substrata
- A4 – Circalittoral rock and other hard substrata

- A5.145 – *Branchiostoma lanceolatum* in circalittoral coarse sand with shell gravel
- A5.25_FR01 – *Chamelea striatula* and *Dosinia lupina* in circalittoral fine sand
- A5.26_FR01 – *Amphiura filiformis* and *Tellina serrata* in circalittoral fine muddy sand
- A5.242 – *Fabulina fabula* and *Magelona mirabilis* with venerid bivalves and amphipods in infralittoral compacted fine muddy sand
- A5.35_FR01 – *Maldane glebifex* and *Clymene modesta* in circalittoral sandy mud
- A5.37_FR01 – *Nucula sulcata* and *Brissopsis lyrifera* in deep circalittoral sandy mud

Figure 3.4: EUNIS Habitat mapping at the LiftWEC implementation area.

3.2.3 Marine species

The EMODnet Biology (data available between 1983-2016; <https://www.emodnet-biology.eu>) and GBIF (data available between 2002-2019; <https://www.gbif.org>) portals rendered occurrences of 76 marine organisms in the search areas (Figure 3.5), including fish (19 taxa), invertebrates (36 taxa), mammals (7 taxa), and birds (14 taxa) (Table 3.1). Several fish and bird species in the list are included in Rede Natura. Most of the fish, all mammals and all birds are regarded in the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species (<https://www.iucnredlist.org>). Those with higher conservation status are the Balearic Shearwater (*Puffinus mauretanicus*) with “Critically Endangered” status, and the Atlantic

Horse Mackerel (*Trachurus trachurus*) and the Black-legged Kittiwake (*Rissa tridactyla*) with “Vulnerable” status.

Figure 3.5: Search area for marine species occurrence: A. EMODnet portal (search box: North – 47.851°, South – 47.836°, East – 4.341°, West – 4.833°). B GBIF portal (search polygon: 47.94386° N, 4.41354° W; 47.90666° N, 4.55143° W; 47.79207° N, 4.51195° W; 47.84306° N, 4.34717° W; 47.86619° N, 4.35475° W; 47.88528° N, 4.36355° W; 47.9061° N, 4.37599° W; 47.9297° N, 4.39273° W; 47.94386° N; 4.41354° W).

Table 3.1: List of marine organisms in the LiftWEC implementation area. Rede Natura species are marked with an “X”. IUCN Red List Conservation status is given (DD: Data Deficient; LC: Least Concern; NT: Near Threatened; VU: Vulnerable; CR: Critically Endangered).

Group	Sub-group	Scientific name	Rede Natura	IUCN Red List
Fish	Actinopterygians	<i>Arnoglossus laterna</i>		LC
		<i>Callionymus lyra</i>	X	LC
		<i>Callionymus maculatus</i>		LC
		<i>Conger conger</i>	X	LC
		<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>	X	LC
		<i>Merlangius merlangus</i>		LC
		<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	X	LC
		<i>Microchirus variegatus</i>		LC
		<i>Mustelus asterias</i>		NT

		<i>Parablennius gattorugine</i>	X	LC
		<i>Scomber scombrus</i>	X	LC
		<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>		LC
		<i>Solea solea</i>	X	DD
		<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	X	VU
		<i>Trisopterus luscus</i>		
		<i>Trisopterus minutus</i>		
		<i>Zeus faber</i>	X	DD
	Elasmobranchs	<i>Mustelus asterias</i>		NT
		<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>		LC
Invertebrates	Annelids			
	Polychaetes	<i>Labioleanira yhleni</i>		
		<i>Nephtys caeca</i>		
		<i>Nephtys hystricis</i>		
		<i>Notomastus latericeus</i>		
		<i>Owenia fusiformis</i>		
		<i>Pectinaria belgica</i>		
		<i>Polycirrus aurantiacus</i>		
		<i>Scoletoma impatiens</i>		
		<i>Spiophanes kroyeri</i>		
		<i>Sternaspis scutata</i>		
	Anthozoans	Actiniaria		
	Ascidians	<i>Botryllus schlosseri</i>		
	Echinoderms			
	Echinoids	<i>Brissopsis lyrifera</i>		
	Holothuroids	<i>Leptopentacta elongata</i>		
		<i>Leptosynapta inhaerens</i>		
	Asteroids	<i>Marthasterias glacialis</i>		
	Molluscs			
	Bivalves	<i>Abra nitida</i>		
		<i>Corbula gibba</i>		
		<i>Gari depressa</i>		
		<i>Myrtea spinifera</i>		
		<i>Mysia undata</i>		
		<i>Thyasira sp.</i>		
	Cephalopods	<i>Loligo forbesii</i>		
		<i>Loligo vulgaris</i>		
	Gastropods	<i>Calliostoma zizyphinum</i>		
		<i>Trivia monacha</i>		
		<i>Turritella communis</i>		

	Scaphopods	<i>Antalis novemcostata</i>			
	Crustaceans				
	Amphipods	<i>Ampelisca brevicornis</i>			
	Cumaceans	<i>Diastylis rugosa</i>			
	Decapods	<i>Nephrops norvegicus</i> <i>Cancer pagurus</i> <i>Goneplax rhomboides</i> <i>Homarus gammarus</i> <i>Maja brachydactyla</i> <i>Pontophilus sp.</i>			
Mammals	Cetaceans	<i>Delphinus delphis</i>	X	LC	
		<i>Globicephala melas</i>	X	LC	
		<i>Halichoerus grypus</i>	X	LC	
		<i>Phocoena phocoena</i>	X	LC	
		<i>Tursiops truncatus</i>	X	LC	
	Carnivores	Phocidae			LC
		<i>Phoca sp.</i>	X (<i>Phoca vitulina</i>)		LC (<i>Phoca vitulina</i>)
	Birds	Charadriiformes	<i>Arenaria interpres</i>	X	LC
			<i>Larus argentatus</i>	X	LC
			<i>Larus fuscus</i>	X	LC
<i>Larus marinus</i>			X	LC	
<i>Larus ridibundus</i>			X	LC	
<i>Rissa tridactyla</i>			X	VU	
<i>Stercorarius skua</i>			X	LC	
<i>Sterna hirundo</i>			X	LC	
<i>Sterna sandvicensis</i>			X	LC	
<i>Uria aalge</i>			X	LC	
Suliformes		<i>Morus bassanus</i>			LC
Procellariiformes		<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>	X		LC
		<i>Puffinus mauretanicus</i>	X		CR
		<i>Puffinus puffinus</i>	X		LC

3.3 HUMAN ACTIVITIES AND USES

The Audierne Bay is shared by a few municipalities, from Audierne (3804 inhabitants) in the Northern part to Penmarch (5614 inhabitants) in the Southern part. Municipalities in the area have their economy based on tourism (<https://www.france-voyage.com>). On land, local heritage includes megalithic monuments, churches, museums, and lighthouses. Most beaches have excellent quality of bathing water, and several coastal recreational activities are developed there (e.g., swimming, diving, water sports, fishing, sailing, yachting) (Figure 3.6).

Figure 3.6: Quality of bathing water and average density of sailing vessels at the Audierne Bay (2019) (<https://emodnet.eu/en/human-activities>).

The bay registers another major source of income to the inhabitants, by use of the maritime space for fisheries (and, in much lower extent, aquaculture) (Figure 3.7).

Figure 3.7: FAO fishery zones (blue lines), average density of fishing vessels (colour scale), and shellfish aquaculture (shell symbols) in or close to the Audierne Bay (<https://emodnet.eu/en/human-activities>).

Routes of telecommunication lines are too found in the area foreseen for the installation of LiftWEC in the Audierne Bay (Figure 3.8).

Figure 3.8: Routes of telecommunication lines (red lines) in the Audierne Bay (<https://emodnet.eu/en/human-activities>).

4 ANALYSIS OF POTENTIAL IMPACTS AND MITIGATION

The evaluation of impact significance is important to determine the resources that should be applied in preventing or mitigating negative impacts or those that maintain or improve positive impacts.

To assess an impact significance, several characteristics of the impact can be considered, for example:

- Direction: Negative, Positive
- Incidence: Direct, Indirect
- Likelihood: Certain, Probable, Uncertain
- Duration: Permanent, Temporary
- Frequency: Frequent, Seasonal, Occasional, Rare
- Temporal scale: Immediate, Mid-term, Long-term
- Spatial scale: Global, Transborder, National, Regional, Local, Adjacent
- Reversibility: Irreversible, Reversible (totally or partially)
- Possibility of Mitigation: Non-mitigatable, Partial, Total
- Importance: High, Moderate, Low
- Magnitude: High, Moderate, Low
- **Significance: Major, High, Moderate, Low, Negligible**

The definition of impact significance involves expert judgement and is subject to interpretations about whether, and to what extent, a proposal is environmentally significant. The key significance levels may be classified as “negligible” when the change does not have a discernible effect, “minor” when effects tend to be discernible but tolerable and unlikely to require mitigation, “moderate” when the changes are considered adverse and thus require mitigation, and “major” when the effects are highest in magnitude and reflect the high vulnerability and importance of the receptor, and thus require mitigation. Those impacts that are classified as moderate or major are considered to be significant (BSI, 2015).

Different options can be used to assess the degree of significance of an impact, for example:

- Use a matrix as proposed by Leopold (1971), in which the project characteristics/activities (stressors) are listed in the columns and the environmental and socioeconomic factors (receptors) are listed in the rows. The interaction of each stressor with each receptor is then scored to indicate the magnitude (1-10) and importance (1-10) of the impact and the combination of the two is used to assess the significance of the impact (Figure 4.1).
- Use a stepwise method, e.g. as proposed by Tagliani and Walter (2018) (Figure 4.2).

	Industrial sites and buildings	Highways and bridges	Transmission lines	Blasting and drilling	Surface excavation	Mineral processing	Trucking	Emplacement of tailings	Spills and leaks
Water quality				2/2	1/1		2/2	1/4	
Atmospheric quality					2/3				
Erosion	2/2			1/1			2/2		
Deposition, Sedimentation	2/2			2/2			2/2		
Shrubs				1/1					
Grasses				1/1					
Aquatic Plants				2/2			2/3	1/4	
Fish				2/2			2/2	1/4	
Camping and hiking				2/4					
Scenic views and vistas	2/3	2/1	2/3	3/3			2/1	3/3	
Wilderness qualities	4/4	4/4	2/2	1/1	3/3	2/5	3/5	3/5	
Rare and unique species		2/5	5/10	2/4	5/10	5/10			
Health and safety						3/3			

Figure 4.1: Matrix method the assessment of impacts significance (from: Leopold, 1971).

Figure 4.2: Stepwise method for the assessment of impacts significance (from: Tagliani and Walter, 2018).

In the present case, a method similar to the Leopold matrix was followed, considering only the expected negative impacts (for all foreseen impacts the reader is referred to Deliverable 9.1). Each negative impact potentially coming from the LiftWEC installation was evaluated for its significance by four researchers to whom was asked to assign a value from 1 (low importance) to 5 (high importance), relating to a “least impacting scenario” and a “major impacting scenario”, respectively. For example, the Stressor “chemical/oil/fuel spill” coming from any activities will result in impacts with variable significance if we consider common fuel release to sea during normal vessel manoeuvres (least impacting scenario) or if a major oil spill from an unexpected leakage or from an accident occurs (major impact scenario). As another example, concerning to the Stressor “visual impact”, impact significance can vary if the activity which poses the stressor is well accepted (least impacting scenario) or very badly accepted (major impacting scenario) by local communities. Finally, a set of 5 classes of negative impacts (Major, High, Moderate, Low, Negligible) was generated.

Table 4.1 presents the stressors and associated receptors for which impacts were classified as High or Major¹⁴ regarding the worst-case scenario. Table 4.2 presents mitigation measures suggested for those impacts.

¹⁴ In the present assessment, High and Major impacts can be described as:

Environmental: Degradation to the quality or availability of habitats and/or wildlife with expected recovery taking more than 2 years (High) or more than 5 years (Major).

Socio-economical: Change to commercial activity leading to loss (High) or great loss (Major) of income or opportunity beyond normal business variability/risk. Potential short-term (High) or mid-term (Major) effect upon public health/well-being.

Table 4.1: Most significant impacts coming from the LiftWEC installation. Significance colour – Light Orange: Low; Dark orange: Moderate; Red: High; Black: Major.

Project development phase	Activity	Stressor	Receptor	Key effects	Significance range	
Preparation	All project activities	Project development in the region	Socioeconomic	Negative perception of the effect of local environmental impacts	Light Orange	Red
			- Local communities - Economic activities	Negative perception of the effect of environmental impacts on commercial activities		
	Loss of equipment or structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	Socioeconomic	Risk of collision with sea users	Light Orange	Red
			- Local communities - Economic activities	Hazards to navigation Potential disruption to economic activities		
	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	Physical	Increase in turbidity	Light Orange	Red
			- Water column	Deterioration of water quality		
			Physical	Disruption of seabed morphology		
- Seabed			Deterioration of sediment quality			
Surveying	Sonar/Seismic surveys	Physical	Changes in the material added to/removed from shoreline, affecting local topography	Light Orange	Red	
		- Shoreline	Death of organisms			
		Biological	Loss of Biodiversity Reduction in productivity			
Construction	All project activities	Project development in the region	Biological	Disruption of behaviour	Light Orange	Red
			- Benthic communities - Fish & Turtles - Marine mammals	Potential harm		
		Chemical/oil/fuel spill	Physical	Deterioration of water quality	Light Orange	Red
			- Water column	Deterioration of sediment quality		
			- Seabed	Potential toxic response		
Socioeconomic	Potential pollution of public spaces (e.g. sandy/rocky shorelines) Potential disruption to economic activities	Light Orange	Red			
- Local communities - Economic activities						

	Loss of equipment or structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	Socioeconomic - Local communities - Economic activities	Risk of collision with sea users Hazards to navigation Potential disruption to economic activities		
	Installation of wave device and subsystems	Installation of WEC - Piling/drilling activities	Physical - Water column - Seabed	Increase in turbidity Deterioration of water quality Disruption of seabed morphology Deterioration of sediment quality		
			Biological - Benthic communities	Death of organisms Loss of biodiversity Reduction in productivity		
			Biological - Fish & Turtles	Disruption of behaviour Potential harm from noise Potential harm from suspended particles (e.g., contaminants)		
			Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour Potential harm from noise		
			Socioeconomic - Local communities - Economic activities	Marine spatial restrictions for sea users (e.g., loss of fishery areas)		
	Transport of wave device and subsystems	Presence of machinery/equipment	Socioeconomic - Local communities - Economic activities	Marine spatial restrictions for sea users		
		Vessel activity	Biological - Marine mammals	Disruption of behaviour Potential physical harm Potential harm from noise		
Operation	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	Physical - Water column - Seabed	Deterioration of water quality Deterioration of sediment quality		
			Biological - Benthic communities - Fish & Turtles - Marine mammals	Potential toxic response		
			Socioeconomic - Local communities - Archaeological sites - Land/Seascape - Economic activities	Potential pollution of public spaces (e.g., sandy and rocky shorelines) Potential pollution of sites with archaeological importance Visual impact Potential disruption to economic activities		
	Loss of equipment or structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	Physical - Water column - Shoreline	Disruption and littering of surface waters Disruption and littering of shoreline		

Presence of WEC device, structural components, and subsystems	Electromagnetic fields	Socioeconomic	Risk of collision with sea users	Yellow	Red	
		- Local communities				
	Presence of WEC device, structural components, and subsystems	Socioeconomic	Hazards to navigation	Orange	Red	
			- Economic activities			Potential disruption to economic activities
		Biological	Disruption of behaviour	Orange	Red	
			- Fish & Turtles			
		Physical	Disruption of seabed morphology	Orange	Red	
			- Seabed			
Biological	Non-indigenous species	Orange	Black			
	- Benthic communities			Invasive species		
Biological	Risk of collision, entanglement, entrapment	Yellow	Red			
	- Fish & Turtles					
Socioeconomic	Marine spatial restrictions for sea users (e.g., loss of fishery areas)	Red	Black			
	- Local communities					
Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	Biological	Yellow	Red	
			- Benthic communities			Potential toxic response
Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	- Fish & Turtles	Yellow	Red	
			- Marine mammals			
Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	Socioeconomic	Yellow	Red	
			- Local communities			Potential pollution of public spaces (e.g., sandy and rocky shorelines)
Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	- Archaeological sites	Yellow	Red	
			- Landscape/Seascape			Potential pollution of sites with archaeological importance
Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	- Economic activities	Yellow	Red	
						Visual impact
Decommissioning	All project activities	Chemical/oil/fuel spill		Yellow	Red	
						Potential disruption to economic activities
Loss of equipment or structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	Socioeconomic	Risk of collision with sea users	Yellow	Red	
			- Local communities			Hazards to navigation
			- Economic activities			Potential disruption to economic activities

Table 4.2: Mitigation measures suggested for the most significant impacts coming from the LiftWEC installation.

Project development phase	Stressor	Receptor	Mitigation
Preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	Physical - Water column - Seabed - Shoreline Biological - Benthic communities	- Mathematical model simulations to predict impacts - Analyse the water and sediment quality and contamination level in surrounding areas before and after dredging - Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required - Select mining areas that cause the least environmental damage and analyse the sediment quality and contamination level in surrounding areas prior to dredging - Mathematical model simulations to predict impacts - Reduce the seabed area to be cleared and restrict it to the immediate vicinity of the project - Eco-efficient surface mining by establishing a depth limit for mining or creation of pits - Employ remediation procedures for contaminated sediment (e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration) - Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments
	Sonar/Seismic surveys	Biological - Benthic communities - Fish & Turtles - Marine mammals	- Soft start ('ramp up') - Delineate safety zones where a temporary shut down or power reduction is triggered in case of observation of turtles or mammals within that area
Construction	Installation of WEC - Piling/drilling activities	Physical - Water column - Seabed	- Mathematical model simulations to predict impacts - Analyse the water and sediment quality and contamination level in the piling area - Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required - Reduce the seabed area to be cleared and restrict it to immediate vicinity of the project, establishing a limit depth to mine - Vibratory piling/drilling could be less-impacting alternatives - Remediation procedures for contaminated sediment (e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration) - Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments
		Biological - Benthic communities - Fish & Turtles - Marine mammals	- Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required - Reduce sound pressure levels using pile caps and vibratory hammers - Attenuate the produced sound using bubble curtains, confined bubble curtains, bubble sleeves, hydro sound dampers or de-watered cofferdams - Remediation procedures for contaminated sediment (e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration) - Use silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments
		Socio-economic - Local communities - Economic activities	- Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required - Disclose the calendar of intervention operations and a plan of restricted areas to the local communities, particularly to fishermen and shipping operators

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduce sound pressure levels using pile caps and vibratory hammers - Attenuate the produced sound using bubble curtains, confined bubble curtains, bubble sleeves, hydro sound dampers or de-watered cofferdams - Seek workers and material acquisition within the local community
	Presence of machinery/equipment	<p>Socioeconomic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local communities - Economic activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Works carried out should be limited to the minimum required - Avoid construction activities during sensitive periods such as busy tourist seasons - Maintain the site clean and ensure its restoration after the activities (onshore)
Operation	Electromagnetic fields	<p>Biological</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fish & Turtles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Avoid sensitive and protected areas - Use adequate cable configuration and sheath/armouring - Increase the distance from the cable to the overlying water whenever possible by burying the cables in the seabed and covering them with boulders, concrete mattresses, or other cover material
	Presence of WEC device, structural components, and subsystems	<p>Physical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Seabed - Water column <p>Biological</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Benthic communities - Fish & Turtles - Marine mammals <p>Socio-economic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local communities - Economic activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitor seabed and sediment quality at the installation area - Monitor changes in wave heights, currents, and water quality at the installation area - Making the devices collapsible could allow using smaller and less specific vessels used in O&M, possibly leading to reduced fuel consumption and antifouling substances released to water - Monitor communities - Ensure an adequate biosecurity risk management plan and regular biofouling-related maintenance activities. This may prevent settlement of invasive or exotic species - Use more environmentally-friendly antifouling techniques - Reduce the risk of collision or entanglement: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - delineate safety zones where a temporary shut down or power reduction is triggered in case of observation of turtles or mammals within that area - keep the device operational speed to the minimum possible - use adequate configurations for electrical cables (e.g. if suspended in the water column use floats becoming more easily visible to animals) and moorings (reasonably taut) - use blunt/thick hydrofoil edges to reduce the harm or mortality on animals caused by potential collision - Implement a strategy of strong public participation (e.g. promote dialogue, enquire the communities, hold public hearings) - Disclose the calendar of maintenance operations and a plan of restricted areas to the local communities, particularly to fishermen and shipping operators - Seek workers and material acquisition within the local community - Provide monetary compensation in case of reduced income caused by interdiction to the maritime space (e.g., preventing fishing activities)
All phases	Project development in the region	<p>Socioeconomic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local communities - Economic activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote strong public participation and communication among local inhabitants, technology developers, decision makers and scientists
	Vessel activity	<p>Physical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water column <p>Biological</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fish & Turtles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduce the impact from vessels to the minimum necessary (e.g. reduce the number of vessels; use modern vessels with adequate, up-to-date maintenance including biofouling removal) - Contracted vessels should carry the tools and material to stop accidental spills and contain the discharged substances

	Marine mammals	Lower vessel speed to reduce noise and reduce collision risk giving opportunity to organisms to evade the area
	Socio-economic	
	- Local communities	- Block the use of the area to other users to minimize risks
Drifting/sinking of equipment	Socioeconomic	- Risk of collision with sea users
	- Local communities	- Hazards to navigation; Potential disruption to economic activities
	- Economic activities	
Chemical/oil/fuel spill	Physical	- Ensure adequate Operations & Maintenance plans and perform regular maintenance activities
	- Water column	- Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop spills and contain the discharged substances on the water surface
	- Seabed	
	Biological	
	- Benthic communities	
	- Fish & Turtles	
	- Marine mammals	
	Socioeconomic	
	- Local communities	
	- Archaeological sites	
	- Landscape/Seascape	
	- Economic activities	

It must be highlighted that OE technologies are in an early stage of development and, although several OE projects have been implemented in the last decade, they were demonstration projects which have not stayed in the water long enough (i.e., several years) to allow monitoring long-term environmental changes caused by the projects (Copping and Hemery, 2020). Consequently, there are many gaps in knowledge about environmental impacts (for example, related with disturbance by noise and electromagnetic fields (EMF) and with seabed disruption) and the impacts described in reports (including the present one) are mostly impacts perceived and broadly acknowledged by the relevant scientific community, but are not measured impacts.

Furthermore, while many effects are expected to be shared across OE projects (for example, seabed disturbance by drilling activities, noise created by vessels and machinery), most effects will be specific to a project, for example depending on the duration of preparation and construction activities, the type of equipment used in such activities, and on site-specific characteristics such as local hydrodynamics.

All uncertainties and gaps in knowledge make Adaptive Management (AM) an extremely useful tool to guide the implementation of monitoring programs. The AM is an iterative process that enables projects to be implemented incrementally in the face of uncertainty about potential impacts, and to assist in closing knowledge gaps through rigorous monitoring and review. If information from routine monitoring shows that the level of an effect is likely to cause an unacceptable impact, corrective actions can be taken. Conversely, if monitoring information indicates that risks have been overestimated, monitoring and mitigation requirements may be reduced (Copping and Hemery, 2020). For example, the impact significances presented in Table 4.1 were the result of an evaluation of expected effects by four researchers which in one hand account for different perspectives, but which also show a range in classes for a particular impact depending on specificities which can only be assessed if/when the impact occurs. In the sense of AM, the significance of impacts and the thresholds between classes, as well as monitoring plans, should be re-evaluated when more monitoring data becomes available and should be redefined if needed.

The following subsections describe the overall potential stressors from the LiftWEC installation and their effects on physical, biological, and socioeconomic receptors.

4.1 PHYSICAL RECEPTORS

4.1.1 Hydrodynamics and water quality

During preparation, construction, and decommissioning activities that imply mining, drilling, piling, and/or anchoring (or removing of all structures in the case of decommissioning), there can be adverse effects on water quality. Together with cable laying on the seabed, such activities will result in increased turbidity, although this should be temporary (e.g., days, depending on wave and current dynamics). Also, they may cause the release of contaminants (where existing) such as heavy metals, trapped in the sediments to the water column.

During the operation phase, devices extract potential or kinetic energy from waves as they pass. The presence of the devices and the energy extraction may result in wave heights being reduced behind arrays (Venugopal et al., 2017). This may influence the availability and transport of gases and nutrients, turbulence levels, as well as the sediment transport and deposition and consequent change in the seabed configuration (for example, changing the grain size composition and associated

retention of organic matter). On the other hand, reduction in waves may result in decreased shoreline erosion.

While most insights into potential changes in hydrodynamics come from numerical modelling, few studies exist that have acquired and compared data from before and after MRE installations. The lack of data in turn hampers the validation of models (Copping and Hemery, 2020). Some studies mention that tidal single MRE devices or small MRE arrays (~20 MW or less) are likely to cause minor changes to hydrodynamics compared to the natural variability of the system (Petrie et al. 2014; Robins et al., 2014). Studies modelling the effect of different configurations of wave WEC arrays have shown significant wave height reduction downstream of the WEC array and farther down the coastline. The possibility of recovery in wave height with increasing distance from the arrays towards the shoreline is uncertain, with different models showing different trends (Iglesias and Carballo, 2014; Venugopal et al., 2017). Overall, it seems that optimizing the spacing of devices within a farm (for example, positioning the devices in a mosaic, as shown in Figure 2.4) may aid in mitigating potential effects on hydrodynamics (Nuernberg and Tao 2018; O’Dea et al., 2019).

Regarding water quality, in all stages of an MRE project, substances such as fuel, mineral oil-based coolants, hydraulic fluids, and antifouling/anticorrosive paintings and coatings of vessels and devices can be released to the ocean by accident and/or lack of equipment maintenance and consequent equipment damage. Such substances can be rapidly dispersed in the immediate water column (Conley et al., 2013). Potential effects caused by leakage of oils or lubricants from vessels and devices can be avoided by ensuring adequate O&M plans and performing regular maintenance activities. Vessels should carry the tools and material to stop accidental spills and contain the discharged substances.

Effects from the use of antifouling paints or coatings can be minimized by employing more environmentally-friendly solutions (e.g., non-copper based) that have been developed in recent years (e.g., Vinagre et al., 2020). These include silicone-based foul release coatings capable of acting against both micro- and macrofouling organisms due to their amphiphilic surface nature, and hydrogel paints which form a water-absorbent polymeric network over the coated surface and make the fouling organisms perceive the coated surface more as a liquid rather than a solid surface (Ciriminna et al. 2015). However, to date, the more environmentally friendly antifouling solutions seem of difficult and expensive application in MRE structures and equipment. And even probably the most environmentally friendly method to control biofouling, which is mechanical cleaning, may have some sort of impact in the marine environment, for example with potential detrimental effects to seabed organisms caused by reduction in oxygen used in the decomposition of dead biofouling organisms in the area. Perhaps, acoustic methods (Legg et al. 2015) or mechanical grooming (e.g., Tribou and Swain 2015), which are quite efficient in the shipping sector, performed regularly could be a more environmentally friendly option to be considered.

Some of the ideas already considered for the future LiftWEC devices may help to reduce the impact of LiftWEC on water quality. For example, making the device collapsible could allow using smaller and less specific vessels for transportation (during installation, maintenance, and decommissioning activities) possibly leading to reduced fuel consumption and antifouling substances released to water. Using synthetic lines for moorings could also require smaller vessels, as they are lighter and more easily stowed than chains. Having ways of forecasting waves and lift forces could allow to predict and avoid extreme waves (for example, with temporary shut-down or submergence to close to the seabed)

and damage on the device, thus preventing potential leaks of lubricants or hydraulic fluids caused by the damage.

4.1.2 Seabed

Construction activities that require mining, drilling, piling, and/or anchoring, together with the installation of mooring systems and transmission cables to land, may disrupt the seabed (and impact its biological component), as well as increase sediment suspension and turbidity levels. Techniques used for securing devices require drilling the seabed (for example impact piling). In those cases, vibratory piling/drilling would be an alternative. Less impacting are the gravity or suction foundations, and thus should be considered in the first place.

Seabed morphology in offshore areas changes naturally in a day-to-day basis (especially closer to land), and changes associated to cable sweeping on the seabed might be cancelled quickly. Cable laying, either for bottom-based or floating devices, is expected to be less impacting to the seabed than other human activities, such as bottom fishing or deep-sea mining (Taormina et al. 2018). Depending on the methods for burying cables in the soft sediment (jetting and especially ploughing seem the less disturbing), resuspended sediment tends to settle in a matter of days (Taormina et al., 2018).

During preparatory and construction activities it should be considered reducing the seabed area to be cleared to the minimum possible and restricting it to immediate vicinity of the project, establishing a limit depth to mine and choosing anchors based on a minimum practical depth into the sediment, and using silt screens to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments.

During operation, the frequent sweeping of the seabed by the moorings/cables used to secure floating devices in site, driven by wave action, may have adverse effects on the seabed morphology and composition, disrupt benthic habitats, and harm or kill marine organisms directly through physical damage of benthic organisms and/or indirectly by the increase in turbidity which will affect pelagic organisms. Hence, it is necessary to ensure adequate cable burying and/or mattresses to reduce cable sweeping to the minimum.

4.2 BIOLOGICAL RECEPTORS

4.2.1 Physical presence of equipment

4.2.1.1 *Change in benthic habitat and communities*

During the preparation and construction phases, portions of the seabed are removed for the placement of the foundation and device itself (bottom-based type) or the anchors/supports (floating type), and to deploy the submarine cables that transport electricity to the onshore substation. This may result in a localized habitat loss and crushing, damaging, or displacement of benthic organisms. Additionally, increased levels of turbidity due to suspension of sediments may decrease light availability and affect photosynthetic organisms, reducing primary productivity and affecting the food web locally. The magnitude of these effects on benthic communities will depend on the duration and intensity of disturbance and the resilience of the local infauna (Drabsch, 2001).

While the seabed configuration and composition may recover in a short period, benthic habitats and communities will take much longer. The recovery timeframe for benthic communities is difficult to distinguish from natural variability (Dunham et al. 2015; Kraus and Carter 2018; Sheehan et al. 2018)

and in some cases recovery has taken one to eight years after cable laying (Kraus and Carter, 2018; Sheehan et al., 2018; Taormina et al., 2018). Overall, although several MRE, and especially OE, projects have been implemented in the last decade, they have not stayed in the water long enough (i.e., several years) to allow monitoring long-term changes caused in the seabed by the projects (Copping and Hemery, 2020). As mentioned in section 4.1.2, the impacted area of seabed could be reduced by different manners which will also reduce the impact on the benthic habitats and communities, namely reducing the area to be cleared to the minimum possible, establishing minimum practical depth for anchoring, and using silt screens to limit the dispersion of sediments.

During the operational phase, if hydrodynamic conditions are affected by the presence of devices, it may influence the transport of food for some species and interfere with the distribution of others with dispersive juvenile stages reliant on transport by currents (Greaves et al., 2016). Depending on the depth at which devices are set to operate, the turbulence and forces generated above the equipment may increase water mixing which affects the water temperature, dissolved oxygen, and nutrients content, as well as may impact plankton communities (Dannheim et al., 2019). On the other hand, if the equipment is set close to the seabed, turbulence and forces generated below the equipment may cause resuspension of sediments and affect the seabed composition and the organisms that live there.

Any artificial structure placed at sea, such as those from the MRE sector, will create a variety of habitats available for a range of organisms, acting as artificial reefs. Positive effects are anticipated with an increase of local biomass and biodiversity (Coolen et al., 2020), for example by providing a hard substrate for macroalgae settlement, colonization by many marine invertebrates, and attracting/aggregating organisms from higher trophic levels, such as fish and marine mammals (Langhamer, 2016; Taormina et al., 2018; Birchenough and Degraer, 2020). Often, these structures show greater diversity and abundance of organisms compared to surrounding areas that are generally made of sandy seabed (Coates et al., 2014). Colonization of the LiftWEC devices and other equipment by encrusting organisms may aid in faster recovery of the communities impacted during preparatory and construction phases. The propagation of non-native species may be prevented by ensuring an adequate biosecurity risk management plan and regular biofouling-related maintenance activities.

However, artificial reefs might also lead to negative ecological and economic effects. It may allow for the settlement and propagation of non-native species, which can use the artificial structures as stepping-stones (Adams et al., 2014; de Mesel et al., 2015) and may spread across the oceans. The colonization of artificial structures by non-native species may affect local organic matter loading, habitat structure and native community composition, with consequences on local biodiversity and food web structure and subsequently on ecosystem services (Coates et al., 2014; Dannheim et al., 2019).

Although several MRE, and especially OE, projects have been implemented in the last decade, they have not stayed in the water long enough (i.e., several years) to allow monitoring long-term changes caused in the seabed by the projects (Copping and Hemery, 2020).

4.2.1.2 Risk of collision

Collision risk will be present during all stages of an MRE project development (including LiftWEC). First, owed to the increased traffic in vessels which are used to transport the equipment and perform maintenance activities. Second, because the physical presence of equipment and anchoring, mooring and cables may create the possibility of collision, impingement or entrapment by mainly marine

mammals and fish, but also by turtles and diving birds (Cada et al., 2007; Wilson et al., 2007). Collision with the pressure field created by the devices might also occur.

The probability of collision with vessels can be reduced by lowering its speed when going to the implementation site, giving an opportunity to animals to evade the area.

Limited information about real numbers of collisions with OE installations is available and the likely consequences of collisions are greatly unknown (Copping and Hemery, 2020). Collision with equipment or its pressure field and entanglement with cables is rare (Laws and Epps, 2016; Sudderth et al., 2017; Copping and Hemery, 2020). It is likely that a hydrofoil technology (oscillating wing-shaped hydrofoil) presents low risk of strike for fish and other marine animals (Sudderth et al., 2017). For example, for tidal devices Sudderth et al. (2017) mentioned that having a low operational speed, for example <math><4.5\text{ m/s}</math>, should reduce the probability of collision or entanglement to very low. Considering the different conditions at which tidal and WE devices operate, it is possible that the probability of an encounter of marine animals with WE devices operating at open sea is similar or lower compared to tidal devices, even at the 6-12 m/s estimated for LiftWEC. In addition, using adequate configurations for electrical cables (for example, suspended in the water column using floats becoming more easily visible to animals) and moorings (reasonably taut) (Copping and Hemery, 2020) would contribute to reduce the probability of collision or entanglement. Finally, the risk of collision can be minimized or eliminated by delineating safety zones where a temporary shut down or power reduction is triggered in case of observation of turtles or mammals within that area. In case of potential collision, using blunt/thick hydrofoil edges should reduce the harm and mortality on animals (Sudderth et al., 2017).

4.2.1.3 Underwater noise

MRE installations generate noise and vibrations, both in the air and underwater, mainly through preparatory and construction activities (from mining, drilling, and piling) and vessels movement. During the operation phase, the noise levels will be very much reduced in comparison to the other phases, coming from the moving components in the project (WEC, mooring, cables).

Considering that acoustic signals can travel longer distances underwater, some marine animals may be affected by noise pollution coming from kilometres away (Frid et al., 2012; Greaves et al., 2016). Mammals and fish particularly take advantage of sound propagation conditions in marine environments for communication, social interaction, orientation, predation, and evasion. Hence, noise disturbance might increase the likelihood of these organisms to collision with OE installations (Wilson et al., 2007).

Several studies have found that the noise generated by MRE installations should have minimal impact (if any) to marine animals (e.g., Thomsen et al., 2015; Tougaard, 2015; Sudderth et al., 2017; Copping and Hemery, 2020), even during the construction phase except possibly in cases where pile driving is used (Thomsen et al., 2015). Further studies are needed to ascertain the existence of detrimental effects, and their magnitude, from noise generated by MRE installations to marine animals, especially considering arrays of devices (Copping and Hemery, 2020).

If piling is necessary to implement LiftWEC, the noise from those activities can be reduced at the source for example by using vibratory hammers and sound dampers and reduced in the water column for example using bubble curtains.

4.2.1.4 Electromagnetic fields

The electricity generated by MRE devices is carried to land substations by submarine cables which produce and emit EMF, the intensity of which depends on the amount of electricity running through the cables (i.e., the cable rating). The ability to sense and respond to EMF is characteristic of many marine organisms that sense either electric fields (E-fields), magnetic fields (B-fields), or both. Cetaceans, migratory fish (for example, salmon and eel), turtles and some crustaceans use Earth's natural geomagnetic fields for undertaking large-scale migrations or orientation (Lohmann et al., 2008; Gill et al., 2012; Newton et al., 2019). Other organisms such as elasmobranchs (sharks, rays, and skates) and agnathans (lampreys) have a sensory apparatus to detect and respond to very low-frequency bioelectric fields emitted by prey or mates and for orientation (Collin and Whitehead, 2004).

The EMFs created at MRE installation areas may attract or repel both magneto-sensitive and electro-sensitive organisms (Boehlert and Gill, 2010; Huveneers et al., 2013; Gill et al., 2014) and may affect the development, physiology, and/or behaviour of sensitive fish and invertebrate species (Hutchinson et al., 2018; Iglesias et al., 2018).

However, data about environmental impacts from EMF are scarce and there is not enough evidence to determine if there are significant negative impacts, especially long-term physiological, biochemical, or behavioural effects, as a consequence of interaction between organisms and EMF generated from MRE installations (Gill et al., 2014; Hutchison et al., 2018; Copping and Hemery, 2020).

Nonetheless, EMF emission from cables can be reduced for example using adequate cable configuration and sheath/armouring and increasing the distance from the cable to the overlying water whenever possible by burying the cables in the seabed and covering them with boulders, concrete mattresses, or other cover material. Also, sensitive and protected areas should be avoided.

4.3 SOCIOECONOMIC RECEPTORS

4.3.1 Local communities and economic activities

The main economic activities in coastal regions are usually fishing, navigation, tourism, industry, and services (Simas et al., 2013a, b). While some of these sectors may be negatively affected by MRE installations (for example, the fishing and tourism sectors), other sectors may benefit from such kind of projects (for example, industry and services).

During the construction phase, the sea use is completely interdicted to avoid vessel accidents and for safe deployment of devices, restricting other activities in a delimited area. These interdictions will have a temporary nature. However, during the whole project exclusion zones are created and possible fishing areas, which are many times the primary income of local communities, are reduced. While this may benefit local marine species populations (for example of fish and crustaceans) and potentially allow for their recovery in the installation area (Krone et al., 2017; van Hal et al., 2017), it may lead to an increasing fishing pressure in nearby areas because of redistribution of fishing effort (Berkenhagen et al., 2010; Stelzenmüller et al., 2011). During the operational phase, an MRE installation will still occupy a large area of maritime space and although exclusion zones are much smaller than in earlier phases they are still implemented. Hence, the fishing sector remains with loss of exploitation areas. The main receptors affected negatively should be the local communities and businesses that rely on fishing as their sole or primary income. To these, it could be suggested after discussions with local

Government representatives and authorities a nearby fishing area to the LiftWEC project area which will be restricted to other users. Also, it could be subject to a monetary compensation to make up for the reduced income from fishing.

Only after decommissioning a restoration of the excluded zones is predicted, allowing for the entire use of maritime space by other coastal users. Then, some negative impacts stated during the construction and operation phases can be reverted, for example eliminating the potential conflict of uses by the local population and increasing job opportunities for the transport and dismantlement of the device and structural components.

Besides the impact on fishing, other concerns raised by local stakeholders include impacts on navigational safety, marine recreation, tourism, and property values (Bonar et al., 2015). The development of MRE projects generally imply coastal restrictions to carry out construction activities such as the cable laying to the onshore substation, and interdiction zones will temporally prevent inhabitants and tourists from the practice of beach sports and leisure activities. In addition, the works for the cable path and the substation itself may disturb residents by increase of noise and traffic, and by potential loss in aesthetics and decrease of property value.

Positive effects are foreseen as a consequence of MRE projects implementation, especially concerning to an enhancement of industries and services locally and potentially at regional and national levels. Opportunities for new businesses and services, such as transport operations, placement of equipment, manufacture of components, and export markets should arise together with creation of jobs (Dalton et al., 2015). Nonetheless, there may be the possibility that the skills required are highly specialised and not found locally, leading to the recruitment of people from abroad instead of local work force.

In all cases, public participation (meetings, enquiries, and general dialog) must be ensured with the local population and stakeholders to minimize negative perception of the project. The public is generally supportive of developing alternative energy sources namely for offshore projects, especially if they have reduced visual impact (DONG Energy et al., 2006; Ladenburg, 2008; Dalton et al., 2015). Early information dissemination (previous to and during the development of projects) to all interested parties (for example, local inhabitants, technology developers, decision makers, scientists) via two-way communication methods contributes to achieving public acceptability most effectively (Chozas et al., 2010; Bonar et al., 2015).

To achieve public acceptability, a good planning of participation strategy should be in place, where dialogues with many kinds of interest groups, in particular neighbours and non-governmental organizations can generate a widespread understanding and social acceptance of the LiftWEC project, including the chosen location, chosen technology and layout of the array. In public hearings, issues such as noise impact, visual impact, and risk of collisions of the LiftWEC wave array should be carefully addressed. Visual impact is usually addressed through a visualisation campaign, where two images are shown: one showing the seascape without the wave array, and another one showing the seascape with the array. Hence, a direct comparison can be made.

4.3.2 Archaeological/protected sites

A preliminary project site survey should inform the eventual presence of cultural patrimony sites. In case of identification of such sites, any intrusive action in land or submersed sites of archaeological or

biodiversity conservation interest might put these preserved areas at risk. Generally, project developers are able to avoid archaeological or protected sites intentionally.

No impact from LiftWEC is foreseen to archaeological or protected sites if surveys are performed previously to preparatory activities to assess the presence of such sites and if they are avoided when implementing the project.

4.3.3 Landscape/seascape

Every MRE installation includes terrestrial and maritime components, therefore potential impacts on the visual amenity in natural sceneries might overcome. Visual impact should be most significant during preparatory, construction and decommissioning activities owed to disruption of landscapes/seascapes of relevant interest and to the increase in vessel activity.

Visual pollution on land might be expected from terrestrial infrastructures such as the electrical substation. Issues related to landscape might be minimized by ensuring that the site aesthetics is compromised at minimal levels, for example maintaining the site clean and ensuring its restoration after the construction activities. Furthermore, construction activities should be avoided during sensitive periods such as busy tourist seasons.

Regarding seascape, although greater visual impact is expected during preparatory, construction and decommissioning activities, that impact will be temporary. During the operational phase, some maritime components might represent visual pollution but only if they are deployed visible to users (for example, nearshore and not submerged in seawater). No impact from LiftWEC to the seascape is foreseen if the project is implemented far away from the coastline and if all equipment (except for marking buoys necessary to identify the project area) is placed submerged.

4.4 CUMULATIVE IMPACTS

Cumulative impacts can be defined as “the accumulation of changes in environmental systems over time and across space in an additive or interactive manner” (Spaling, 1994). Cumulative impacts can result from multiple impacts from the same project (e.g., OE multiple-unit deployment) or the combined impacts of multiple developments (e.g., OE, aquaculture, fishing, and shipping activities in the same area).

Concerning to OE projects (but not only), impacts that may be negligible for one or a few units may become significant for multiple-unit deployment. However, as opposed to the effects of individual stressors on individual receptors, effects from large developments (both spatially and temporally) remain greatly unexplored leading to increased uncertainty (Willsteed et al., 2017; Copping and Hemery, 2020). This is further aggravated considering that the new OE projects will probably be implemented in areas already affected by anthropogenic activities for decades or centuries (Willsteed et al., 2017).

Cumulative effects can result from temporal accumulation or spatial accumulation. Temporal accumulation refers to change brought about by disturbances or perturbations accumulating as the period between perturbations is shorter than the period of ecological recovery. Temporal accumulation can occur in a continuous, periodic, or irregular manner and occur over long or short time scales (Willsteed et al., 2017). Spatial accumulation takes place where the effects of perturbations overlap in space, as the space between perturbations is less than that required to

disperse the disturbance. Spatial accumulation can occur over variable scales, from local to regional to global (Willsteed et al., 2017).

The AM allows for predictive modelling, environmental monitoring, and phased deployment to be adjusted to reflect the findings of the previous monitoring. Hence, as projects expand from small, demonstration scales to commercial developments, the use of an AM framework could be an effective means of resolving particular issues and addressing cumulative effects (US Department of Energy, 2009). A major limitation of AM is that a detectable change in the resource(s) of concern must occur before there can be a change in management. Nonetheless, in many cases the most efficient approach is to focus on minimizing the effects of individual action. Considering that the largest effect of a given action is usually local and immediate, such effect can be most easily detected at smaller spatial and temporal scales, thus reducing its extent in both scales (MacDonald, 2000).

5 MONITORING POTENTIAL NEGATIVE IMPACTS

There are plenty techniques/equipment that can be used to monitor the impacts from OE and other developments. Table 5.1 provides a summarized list of parameters to be monitored and the techniques used for the most significant impacts (presented in Table 4.1). The following sections provide additional information on monitoring.

Table 5.1: List of monitoring parameters and techniques for the most significant impacts (see Table 4.1).

Project development phase	Stressor	Receptor	Monitoring parameters	Monitoring Techniques
Preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	Physical - Water column	Depth Turbidity Temperature Salinity Chlorophyll a Dissolved oxygen Nutrients Contaminants	Desk based analysis In situ probes In situ CTD casting Water sampling and laboratory analysis Modelling
		Physical - Seabed - Shoreline	Seabed morphology Sediment movement Sediment composition and granulometry Sediment organic matter Sediment contaminants	Desk based analysis GIS analysis Active acoustics – SONARs Modelling
		Biological - Benthic communities	Parameters above for water and sediment Species composition, diversity, abundance (density and biomass)	Techniques above for water and sediment Modelling of impacts
		Sonar/Seismic surveys	Biological - Benthic communities - Fish & Turtles - Marine mammals	None in particular

Construction	Installation of WEC - Piling/drilling activities	Physical - Water column	Depth Turbidity Temperature Salinity Chlorophyll a Dissolved oxygen Nutrients Contaminants	Desk based analysis In situ probes In situ CTD casting Water sampling and laboratory analysis Modelling
		Physical - Seabed	Seabed morphology Sediment movement Sediment composition and granulometry Sediment organic matter Sediment contaminants	Desk based analysis GIS analysis Active acoustics – SONARs Modelling
		Biological - Benthic communities - Fish & Turtles - Marine mammals	Species composition, diversity, abundance (density, biomass, coverage, presence/absence), distribution, presence of invasive species	Modelling of impacts
		Socio-economic - Local communities - Economic activities	Level of public acceptance	Desk based analysis Modelling Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
	Presence of machinery and/or equipment	Socioeconomic - Local communities - Economic activities	Level of public acceptance	Desk based analysis Modelling Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
Operation	Electromagnetic fields	Biological - Fish & Turtles	Species composition, diversity, abundance (density) and distribution	Photographic sampling (underwater cameras, divers, ROVs) Modelling
	Presence of WEC device, structural components, and subsystems	Physical - Seabed	Sediment composition and granulometry Sediment organic matter Sediment contaminants	Sampling and laboratorial analysis Modelling
		Biological - Benthic communities	Species composition, diversity, abundance (density, biomass, coverage), distribution, presence of invasive species	Sampling and laboratorial analysis Photographic sampling (underwater cameras, divers, ROVs)
		Biological - Fish & Turtles	Species composition, diversity, abundance (density) and distribution	Sampling, followed by laboratorial analyses Photographic sampling (underwater cameras, divers, ROVs) Active acoustics – SONARs Telemetry tags Modelling
		Biological - Marine mammals	Species composition, diversity, abundance (density and	Observation surveys Passive acoustics – C-Pods Telemetry tags

			presence/absence) and distribution	Modelling
		Socio-economic - Local communities - Economic activities	Level of public acceptance	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)
All phases	Project development in the region	Socioeconomic - Local communities - Economic activities	Level of public acceptance Number of direct and indirect jobs created (quantifying highly specialized ones) Number of new businesses created Identification of relevant stakeholders Quantification of avoided GHG emissions Overlap with other marine uses (marine spatial planning analysis)	Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods) Analytical methods (e.g., econometric models) Mapping (GIS) Desk based analysis
	Vessel activity	Physical - Water column Biological - Fish & Turtles - Marine mammals Socio-economic - Local communities	Visual perception/impact	Desk based analysis Participatory methods (e.g., questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)

5.1 OCEANOGRAPHY

Detailed surveys can be carried out to determine the bathymetry, seabed morphology and habitats in the area (including the location of the array and cable route) using high resolution multibeam echo sounders (MBES) or side-scan sonars.

To assess currents velocity and direction, a static Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) survey can be commissioned over at least one month to cover both neap and spring tides. Wave height measurements can be made before the installation of devices and repeated after single and multiple units have been installed. Measured changes in current velocities or wave heights could be used to validate predictive models and help explain concurrent changes in sediment transport and aquatic habitats.

Sediment composition can be characterized by grab sampling and subsequent laboratory analysis of sediment granulometry. Sediment organic matter and the presence of contaminants can be analysed by laboratorial analyses.

Sediment transport dynamics can be modelled to predict the influence of alterations to hydrography locally and towards/on the shoreline. Satellite imagery can be used to identify changes in the seabed (from the installation site to the shoreline) resulting from the modified wave climate.

5.2 BIOLOGICAL RECEPTORS

5.2.1 Benthic habitats and communities

Before the installation of devices, the characterization of local benthic habitats and species may be underrepresented through the information obtained from data portals (e.g., EMODnet). Hence, it is necessary to conduct further baseline characterisation of the area in terms of typical benthic communities that are expected to occur. Seabed habitats and communities can be characterized using non-destructive methods such as mapping and sampling (videos and photographs) by divers or ROVs together with methods of acoustic mapping. Other, more destructive but more thorough, methods include grabs or box-core sampling. This baseline characterization should identify qualitatively (e.g., which species) and quantitatively (e.g., density and biomass of species) and species richness.

During the operational stage, monitoring should focus on specific areas where impacts are likely to occur, using the same techniques (and parameters) applied during the baseline characterisation to allow the comparison of communities before and after the installation (Before-After-Control-Impact design).

5.2.2 Fish, turtles, mammals

The monitoring of fish, turtle or mammal populations dynamics and habitat distribution at both spatial and temporal scales can be done using active acoustic monitoring (AAM; e.g., acoustic cameras, echosounders, single- or multi-beam sonars, telemetry) and passive acoustic monitoring (PAM; e.g., hydrophones, C-PODs). For mammal monitoring, vessel transect surveys and PAM are the most frequent methods used. Auditory masking (the interference of important biological signals by anthropogenic noise) should be assessed in different seasons to evaluate the effects of noise from operational LiftWEC devices on the listening space of marine mammals.

The use of PAM to collect long-term data is very useful, cost-effective, and non-invasive. However, it only provides information about animal presence and does not allow obtaining fine-scale movement data to assess interactions between animals and devices. Using acoustic transmitters (telemetry) allows researchers to determine the animals' movements and occupancy times (although it requires tagging a large number of individuals, e.g. hundreds for fish). In parallel, mathematical models can be used to estimate collision risk (e.g., Wilson et al., 2007; Schmitt et al., 2017) and active sonars and underwater cameras can be used on site to verify the interaction.

Alike for benthic communities, monitoring of fish, turtles or mammals should be undertaken as a Before-After-Control-Impact design using the same techniques and parameters pre- and post-installation of devices or structures.

5.2.3 Birds

Because OE devices are mainly submerged, monitoring is generally focused on diving birds (e.g., Grecian et al., 2010). However, seabirds are subject to different types of pressures and it is difficult to assess the influence of OE projects on their populations.

Studies should be site-specific and focus on vulnerability factors of species with high potential to be affected, the most relevant factors being risk of collision, exclusion from foraging habitat, effects of fish attraction to device or biofouling and disturbance by structures and ship traffic (Furness et al., 2012).

Population dynamics of seabirds can be monitored by traditional visual observation methods, for example carrying out surveys on land and on vessels covering the development site and a buffer zone and covering seasonal variations that reflect breeding, migration, and wintering. Radars and telemetry can be used to assess distribution and diving depths of animals.

5.2.4 Toxicants

Compilation and assessment of information on the toxicity of each chemical associated with the project (e.g., hydraulic fluids, lubricants, antifouling) should be completed. Additionally, the potential for bioaccumulation of toxic compounds (e.g., heavy metals) could be considered and monitored. Where such information is not available, it could be derived from ecotoxicological bioassays.

5.3 SOCIOECONOMIC RECEPTORS

5.3.1 Local communities and economic activities

Baseline data can be gathered through a desk based study to identify the businesses and activities that may be affected by the project. In addition, land based surveys can be carried out to identify the interested parties, how the project may disrupt activities, the number of jobs that will potentially be created throughout the project development, among others.

5.3.2 Archaeological sites

Although in the area foreseen for the installation of LiftWEC no Archaeological sites were found, for the final site a thorough high-resolution multibeam echo sounder survey can be undertaken to ensure that such sites of archaeological importance (e.g., submerged landscapes, ship wrecks, isolated artefacts) do not exist in the area.

5.3.3 Landscape/seascape

It may be recommended that a Visual Assessment is undertaken to determine the effect of the LiftWEC development upon landscape and seascape character of the area.

6 CONCLUDING REMARKS

This deliverable aimed at developing a preliminary Scoping Report for the LiftWEC project EIA. While a full Scoping report requires extensive description of a number of characteristics of a Project, at the moment, not all specifics of the LiftWEC development can be defined as the project is at its mid-stage and the technology is novel and therefore not yet matured.

When/if Scoping is undertaken, a refinement of information will be required, including precise definition of:

- the LiftWEC device, components, and subsystems
- their functioning and operational requirements
- how and where exactly all will be deployed
- the baseline characterization
- the equipment used for and timeframe of marine operations
- the materials used in the project

Although the present report includes information which was generalized from other installations already in operation at sea, it also provides a fairly descriptive analysis of the main topics to consider, and how to address them, for the LiftWEC Scoping and should allow the process to occur with great ease at the time.

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